

**THE MEDIATING ROLE OF HOME ENVIRONMENT ON THE
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LANGUAGE LEARNING
MOTIVATION AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS
AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS**

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The Mediating Role of Home Environment on the Relationship Between Language Learning Motivation and Communication Skills among College Students

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the mediating role of the home environment on the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills among college students. Quantitative non-experimental research utilizing descriptive correlational technique and mediation analysis were employed in this study. The data were gathered from 258 non-board program first-year to third-year students through stratified random sampling utilizing proportional allocation. Data gathering was done through survey questionnaires. The statistical tools used in the computation of data and testing the hypotheses at alpha 0.05 level of significance are mean, Pearson r, and structural equation modelling (SEM) using mediation analysis. Findings revealed that the level of language learning motivation, communication skills, and home environment were high. There was a significant relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills, home environment and communication skills, home environment and language learning motivation. Results also revealed that the home environment has full mediated the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills.

Keywords: *home environment, language learning motivation, communication skills, mediation analysis*

Introduction

Communication skills are essential for interacting with students. Mastering these skills is beneficial in all areas of life, helping to make a positive impression and facilitating clear conversations, both spoken and written. Conversely, poor communication skills can lead to ineffective teaching, resulting in lower student comprehension and potentially hindering their academic progress. This may also cause students to lose motivation, develop a dislike for school, and doubt their abilities, which can have long-term impacts on their lives (Sword, 2023).

In Indonesia, a study conducted at Institut Agama Islam Negeri Syekh Nurjati Cirebon shows that a significant number of students were unable to effectively communicate their learning results. The result shows only 10% are proficient in communicating outcomes adequately. This demonstrates the student's poor communication abilities at SMP Negeri 1 because of their lack of knowledge and fear to make mistakes, some students are hesitant to express themselves in front of the class (Munawaroh et al., 2022).

In Philippines, a study conducted at St. John Colleges in Calamba, Laguna shows that most students are afraid to speak and use the English language because of being afraid to be laughed at and because of their "English Carabao" English has become the second language of the country and the language is being utilized in the classroom setting in terms of delivering instruction to teachers as well as students when doing reporting, recitation, and more (Dela Cruz, 2022).

Based from the readings above, it is evident and observable that weak communication skills is really a problem in global, national, and even in the local setting. This study has a social relevance because having the ability to communicate properly and appropriately serves a crucial role in every college student's life. Effective communication skills pave the way to gain academic prospects, academic success and personal development; ensuring that they are equipped to navigate the complexities of the modern world. On the other hand, the study needs an urgent research attention because weak communication skills can have far-reaching negative effects on students' academic standing since it hinders them to communicate their ideas property which potentially leads to low self-esteem and lower grades. Moreover, poor communication skills can lead to social anxiety and stress among college students. Studying communication skills can help identify those at risk and provide interventions to improve their mental health and well-being. Therefore, this problem needs to be addressed immediately.

In the literature review, it has been found out related studies such as the study of Sabbah et al. (2020) titled "Communication Skills among Undergraduate Students at Al Quds University" and Akyurt (2018) titled "Determination of the Communication Skills of University Students by Sociodemographic Features" only discussed the communication skills of university students from different countries. However, this study is unique from the aforementioned studies because there is no existing study that examines the home environment as a mediator between the linkage of language learning motivation and communication skills. Hence, the aforementioned studies indicate that this current study does not show any irrelevance and redundancy.

Research findings in this study can be used in the formulation of effective pedagogical strategies for it considers the interplay between language learning motivation, the home environment, and communication skills. Educators can adapt teaching methods to improve language learning motivation and communication skills of the students. This research gap is important for educators, administrators, and future researchers as it will contribute to the body of literature not only within the academe but also outside of it, the findings will be disseminated to the various research conferences and related agencies to be realized by the broader community through making

actions and solutions on the problems being discussed as well as implementing the recommendations being suggested here. Moreover, this study was conducted in the Philippines, and this interests the college students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST).

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to examine the mediating role of the home environment on the relationship between language anxiety and communication skills among non-board program college students. To be specific, this study sought answers to the following objectives.

1. To determine the level of language learning motivation in terms of:
 - 1.1. learning needs;
 - 1.2. self-efficacy; and,
 - 1.3. achievement motivation.
2. Determine the acceptability level of the respondents on the utilization of AI on learning process in terms of:
 - 2.1. mental communication skills;
 - 2.2. emotional communication skills; and,
 - 2.3. behavioral communication skills.
3. To determine the level of home environment in terms of:
 - 3.1. friendly home environment;
 - 3.2. home facilities;
 - 3.3. parent's attention or care; and,
 - 3.4. motivational behavior of parents.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. language learning motivation and communication skills;
 - 4.2. home environment and communication skills; and,
 - 4.3. home environment and language learning motivation.
5. To determine the mediating role of home environment on the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills among college students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used quantitative non-experimental research utilizing descriptive- correlational technique alongside mediation analysis. The investigation focused on mediating variables, which are characterized as behavioral, biological, psychological, or social constructs that facilitate the transfer of the effect of one variable to another. This approach aimed to comprehend the mechanisms underlying the influence of one variable on another. Non-experimental research, as described, did not involve the manipulation of an independent variable or the random assignment of individuals to conditions or sequences of conditions. It is acknowledged that categorizing these methods solely based on what they are not might be unfair (Price et al., 2014).

In this study, non-experimental methods were used to investigate the relationship between language learning motivation, communication skills, and home environment among non-board program, students, providing insights for educational strategies, the study can offer valuable insights, which can inform educational strategies and curriculum development in teacher education programs. With little to no effort made to control unrelated variables, correlational research is a type of non- experimental study in which the researcher examines two variables and assesses their statistical relationship (i.e., the correlation). Researchers that are interested in statistical correlations between variables may favor a correlational study over an experiment for two key reasons (Price et al., 2014).

In this study, descriptive statistics were utilized to efficiently summarize and analyze gathered data, providing insights into the central tendencies, variability, and distribution of language learning motivation, communication skills, and home environment within the participant group. These statistics served as a foundation for understanding complex dynamics and identifying patterns, contributing to meaningful conclusions in the study.

Then, on the other hand, correlational research is characterized as a type of non-experimental study where the researcher analyzes two variables and assesses their statistical relationship or correlation with minimal or no attempt to control extraneous factors. There were two primary reasons why researchers who were interested in statistical correlations between variables might prefer to perform a correlational rather than an experimental study (Price et al., 2014).

In the context, correlational research proves valuable in examining statistical relationships between variables like language learning motivation, communication skills, and home environment without manipulating them in a controlled environment. This approach acknowledges the complexity of real-world educational settings, providing insights crucial for tailoring effective teaching strategies to support students' success in mathematics within the constraints of a non-experimental approach.

Mediation analysis, in its simplest form, represented the addition of a third variable to the $X \rightarrow Y$ relation, whereby X caused the

mediator, M, and caused Y, so $X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$. This analytical approach provided a deeper understanding of the mechanisms through which the independent variable affected the dependent variable. By identifying and exploring the role of the mediator, researchers gained insights into the underlying processes and pathways that contributed to the observed relationship between X and Y. Mediation analysis was particularly valuable in uncovering the intervening variables that explained how and why changes in X led to changes in Y.

In this context, the researcher explored the intricate connections between language learning motivation (X), home environment (M), and communication skills (Y). The analysis revealed a relationship ($X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$), illustrating how home environment mediates the influence of language learning motivation. These insights are crucial for customizing teaching strategies and curriculum to optimize language learning of students.

The independent variable in this study was language learning motivation, while the dependent variable was communication skills, and the mediating variable was home environment. In this study, the researcher determined the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills, and the mediating effect of home environment among the non-board program students.

Respondents

The study involved the non-board program students enrolled in the Academic Year 2023-2024 primarily first year to third year students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST). They are chosen as the respondents because the study is about the mediating role of home environment on the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills among college students specifically non-board program students. Also, this period represents a critical phase in language learning and communication skills development. These early years are characterized by significant transitions and adjustments, making it valuable to understand how home environment mediates the link between language learning motivation and communication skills during this formative stage. Additionally, the researcher targets the non-board program students because it has the biggest population in the research locale which will provide a more comprehensible understanding about the mediating role of home environment on the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills. Considering that the student in this program needs to develop their communication skills for future endeavor, this study wants to determine how language learning motivation affects their communication skills as mediated by their home environment.

Furthermore, to establish randomness and maintain the element of science in the study, stratified random sampling utilizing proportional allocation was chosen. The stratified random sampling technique is utilized to obtain a representative sample of a given population. The sampling technique entails partitioning the entire population into smaller, more homogeneous subgroups or strata distinguished by common attributes or characteristics. The methods employed by the researcher involves the random selection of a sample from each stratum in a manner proportional to its size. This approach ultimately yields a representative sample of the population (Hayes, 2023).

In this context, the sampling method employed in this study is particularly appropriate because the respondents of the study were randomly selected based on strata, which are in the case, the students enrolled in non-board programs from the first year to third year. The study employed the stratified sampling method to enhance the precision and accuracy of estimating the sample population, thereby ensuring a representative sample of respondents.

To compute for the sample, the researcher initially obtained data on the population of participants by writing a formal request letter to the College Registrar, seeking permission to access the population of respondents. Upon receiving the data, the researcher sent it to his statistician to compute the study sample. The sample utilized in the study was obtained by using Slovin's Formula with a margin of error of ($e = 0.06$). The formula mentioned determined the appropriate number of sample size for the population of non-board program students.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the population of this study.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Non-board Programs</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelor of Public Administration	915	69	1.98%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	1695	126	3.66%
Bachelor of Science in Office Administration	843	43	1.83%
Total	3453	258	7.47%

Instrument

The study adopted three credible questionnaires to measure the variables. The first set of questions assessed the communication skills with its indicators; mental communication skills, emotional communication skills and behavioral communication skills (Ersanli & Balci, 1998).

The second set of questions focused on the language learning motivation, with its indicators; learning needs, self-efficacy and achieved motivation (Yang et al., 2012). The third set of questions focused on the home environment with its indicators; friendly home environment, home facilities, parents' attention or care and motivational behavior of parents (Younas et al., 2021)

In this study, the Likert scale was used to gauge respondents' agreement or disagreement with each statement, allowing for the gathering of quantitative data on their perceptions of home environment, language learning motivation and communication skills. The respondents were asked to answer to this scale by either checking a point number. The participants responded using a five-point Likert scale and the scores were calculated by adding these values across all the elements.

To easily evaluate the data that was gathered with this study, the researcher made a table that represents the five orderable categories information and communications technology skills with their respective means.

Procedure

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher sought permission from the College President of KCAST through a letter of permission to allow the researcher to conduct the study among first to third year non-board program students. After having the approval of the College President, the researcher sent copies of the letters to the College Registrar and the Vice-President for Academic Affairs.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Upon the approval of the College President, the researcher sought assistance from the Program Coordinators of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration, Bachelor of Science in Office Administration, and Bachelor of Science in Public Administration, as well as their respective class mayors for the dissemination of the questionnaires through a face-to-face administration of the research questionnaires.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. The research instrument was retrieved, examined, accumulated for the tabulation of the data gathered. From the final data, conclusions were drawn, and recommendations were presented based on the results of the study.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data and testing the hypotheses. It includes mean, Pearson r , and structural equation modeling using mediation analysis.

This statistical tool was used to determine the level of language learning motivation, communication skills, and home environment.

Pearson r . This statistical tool was utilized to test the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills; language learning motivation and home environment; and home environment and communication skills.

Structural Equation Modeling using Mediation Analysis. This statistical tool was carried out to figure out whether the home environment has any impact on the relationship between language learning motivation and a communication skills using indirect effect.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of this study were the first-third year non-board students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. In this case, the researcher ensured that their safety, rights, and trust upon the researcher and the purpose of the study were given rightful action and justice.

It is necessary for researcher to uphold high ethical standards when doing research with the involvement of human participants. The primary objective of this quantitative investigation is to ensure the ethical soundness of the study to protect the welfare of human participants. The researcher reflected how the research in all aspects can adhere to the following considerations from Denzin and Lincoln (2011) which focused on three core principles: informed consent; risk of harm, anonymity, and confidentiality; as well as conflict of interest.

Informed consent is the first core principles of ethical considerations. The requirements, the planned use of the data, and any potential ramifications must all be adequately disclosed to participants. Participants must express their explicit, active, and written consent to participate in the study. They must also acknowledge that they are aware of their right to access their information and that they have the right to revoke their consent at any time. An agreement between the researcher and the respondents can be considered in the process of getting informed consent (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Risk of Harm, Maintaining Confidentiality, and Anonymity is the second core principles of ethical considerations. It pertains to the protection of a study's participant so that not even the researcher can link the participants with the data provided, as well as the avoidance of disclosing the participant's identity to anybody other than authorized individuals (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

The participants' safety and confidentiality were of utmost importance. The researcher assured the protection of their identity and personal information, viewing them as valued contributors to the research. To ensure spotless data collection, identities were eliminated, resulting in data free from any identifying information, such as names or addresses. Such identifying details will be securely stored elsewhere in separate, protected files. This rigorous approach ensures the integrity and confidentiality of the participants and the data.

Conflicts of Interest is the third core aspect of ethical considerations. It recognizes the existing relationships or previous activities by the researcher could result in conflict of interest, which must be transparently revealed in an ethics approval application so the committee can provide advise on how to address the conflict. Additionally, it occurs when a person prioritizes their personal interests or commitments over their responsibilities as a researcher or is perceived to prioritize them over their duties and responsibilities.

Conflicts of interest may be actual, hypothetical, or perceived and may involve incentives in money or in nonmonetary rewards. Conflicts of interest may impair a researcher's objectivity and judgment, or may be perceived to affect, which undermines the reliability of the findings (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this view, there was no external factor in relation to the researcher affecting the outcomes of the research activity because the respondents were also students, the researcher has no conflict of interest in the study. Conflict of interest only arises when the researcher has the power to coerce respondents into participating through blackmailing, termination of benefits, or other forms of punishment, such as: teachers who would force or threaten to fail their students if they do not answer the survey, or principals who threaten to terminate teachers if they do not answer the survey.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings and results on the mediating role of the home environment on the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills among college students. Moreover, the interpretations of data were done parallel to the research objectives.

Level of Language Learning Motivation in Terms of Learning Needs

The level of language learning motivation in terms of learning needs was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator assessment is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The response of the respondents on the indicator were presented and analyzed below.

The results on the level of students' language learning motivation in terms of learning needs is revealed and reflected in Table 2 with the corresponding mean score of 4.05. The result of this item indicator is qualitatively interpreted and described as high. This indicates that in terms of learning needs it is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 2. *Level of Language Learning Motivation in Terms of Learning Needs*

	<i>Learning Needs</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Having no language communication problems in speaking English language	3.35	Moderate
2.	Believing that learning English will help me get a better job in the future	4.37	Very High
4.	Thinking that it is necessary to learn English to have a better life	4.09	High
5.	Thinking that learning English well will help me keep up with international current events	4.23	High
6.	Believing that learning English can help me understand different cultures and people	4.22	High
	Overall	4.05	High

Furthermore, it can be observed from the data that the item with the highest mean rating is 4.37. this item is no. 2 – Believing that learning English will help me get a better job in the future. Moreover, it is qualitatively described and interpreted as high. The result of this item indicator is qualitatively interpreted and described as high. This indicates that in terms of learning needs it is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

As opposed to this, the item with the lowest mean rating of 3.35 is item no. 1 - Having no language communication problems in speaking English language. Thus, the result of this item indicator is qualitatively interpreted and described as moderate. This indicates that in terms of learning needs it is sometimes observed by the respondents.

Level of Language Learning Motivation in terms of Self-Efficacy

The level of language learning motivation in terms of self-efficacy was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator assessment is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The response of the respondents on the indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 3. *Level of Language Learning Motivation in Terms of Self-efficacy*

	<i>Self-efficacy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Learning English well	3.85	High
2.	Believing that learning English is a challenge	4.23	High
3.	Being confident that I can speak with others in English	3.35	Moderate
4.	Understanding everything that my teacher says in English	3.74	High
5.	Having a correct English pronunciation	3.21	Moderate
	Overall	3.68	High

The data reflected in Table 3 is the level of the students' level of language learning motivation as perceived by non-board program students in terms of self- efficacy with a corresponding overall mean of 3.68 or qualitatively interpreted as high. The results confirm that the indicator is oftentimes observed by the respondents. It can be observed from the data that the item with the highest mean rating of 4.23 or qualitatively described as high is item no. 2 – Believing that learning English is a challenge. This item is oftentimes observed

by the respondents.

As opposed to this, the item with the lowest mean rating of 3.21 or qualitatively described and interpreted as moderate is item no. 5 – Having a correct English pronunciation. This means that this item is sometimes observed by the respondents.

The Level of Language Learning Motivation in terms of Achievement Motivation

The level of language learning motivation in terms of achievement motivation was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator assessment is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The response of the respondents on the indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Results are reflected in Table 4 is the level of students' language learning motivation as perceived by non-board program students in terms of achievement motivation with corresponding mean of 3.86. The indicator is qualitatively described and interpreted as high. It means that it is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

It can be observed from the data that the item with the highest mean rating 4.24 is item no. 1 – Trying my best to enhance my English proficiency. Moreover, it signifies that the item is qualitatively described as high. This indicates that the item is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

As opposed to this, the item with the lowest mean rating of 3.5 or qualitatively described as high is item no. 4 – Enjoying in learning English because I feel that I am good with it. Moreover, this means that this item is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 4. *Level of Language Learning Motivation in Terms of Achieved Motivation*

	<i>Achieved Motivation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying my best to enhance my English proficiency	4.24	High
2.	Feeling pleased to learn English that is somewhat higher level of difficulty than my current level	3.88	High
3.	Giving my best during recitation using the English language	3.73	High
4.	Enjoying in learning English because I feel that I am good with it	3.56	High
5.	Being careful in planning the words I use whenever I say/write something in English language	3.90	High
	Overall	3.86	High

Summary on the level of Language Learning Motivation

The summary on the level of language learning motivation is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The mean results on each indicator were presented and analyzed.

Reflected in the Table 5 is the results of the data on the level of language learning motivation among college students particularly the non-board program students with an overall mean score of 3.86 described as high. With having indicators: learning needs, self-efficacy and achievement motivation. This indicates that this variable is oftentimes observed by non-board program students.

It can be observed in the table that the indicator, learning needs got the highest mean score of 4.05. this indicates that this item is qualitatively described and interpreted as high. This means that this indicator is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Moreover, on the other hand, the indicator, self-efficacy, got the lowest mean score of 3.68. this indicator is qualitatively described as high. This signifies that this indicator is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 5. *Summary on the Level of Language Learning Motivation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Learning Needs	4.05	High
Self-Efficacy	3.68	High
Achievement Motivation	3.86	High
Overall	3.86	High

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Mental Communication Skills

The level of communication skills in terms of mental communication was measured through survey questionnaire with the indicator assessment is presented, analyzed and interpreted. The response of the respondents on the indicator was presented below.

Reflected in the Table 6 is the level of communication skills in terms of mental communication skills with a corresponding overall mean of 3.83. Moreover, it is qualitatively interpreted and described as high as perceived by the respondents. This indicates that the indicator is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Moreover, it can be observed from the data that the highest mean rating of 4.10 from the item no. 1 – Trying to understand people. Furthermore, it is observed as high as perceived by the respondents.

As opposed to this, the lowest mean rating of 3.48 is from the item no. 2 – Having no difficulty communicating my thoughts exactly

to others. This indicates that this item is oftentimes manifested by the non-board program student.

Table 6. *Level of Communication Skills Terms of Mental Communication Skills*

<i>Mental Communication Skills</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying to understand people.	4.10	High
2.	Having no difficulty communicating my thoughts exactly to others.	3.48	High
3.	Being able to easily accept my wrong attitudes and behaviors.	3.91	High
4.	Repeating what I have said using different words and summarizing it if the person I am talking to does not understand me.	3.66	High
5.	Trying to empathize with the person I am talking in order to understand their feelings and thoughts.	4.01	High
Overall		3.83	High

Level of Communication Skills in terms of Emotional Communication Skills

The level of communication skills in terms of emotional communication skills was measured through survey questionnaires with the indicator assessment is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The response of the respondents on the indicator was presented below.

Reflected in Table 7 is the level of communication skills in terms of emotional communication skills with a corresponding mean of 3.85. Moreover, it is qualitatively interpreted and interpreted as high. This indicates that the indicator is oftentimes manifested by the non-board program students.

Consequently, it could be gleaned from the data that the highest mean rating of 4.35 or Very High is from the item 1 – Feeling happy to be understood by the person I communicate with, which means it is always manifested by the respondents

As opposed to this, the item with the lowest mean rating of 3.45 or Moderate is item no. 4 – Having no trouble communicating my negative feelings.

Table 7. *Level of Communication Skills Terms of Emotional Communication Skills*

<i>Emotional Communication Skills</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Feeling happy to be understood by the person I communicate with	4.35	Very High
2.	Staying energetic while listening to people	3.74	High
3.	Welcoming every other human being with positive expectations	3.99	High
4.	Having no trouble in communicating my negative feelings	3.45	Moderate
5.	Feeling like I am understood by the people I communicate with	3.72	High
Overall		3.85	High

Level of Communication Skills in terms of Behavioral Communication Skills

The level of communication skills in terms of behavioral communication skills was measured through survey questionnaires with the indicator assessment is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The response of the respondents on the indicator was presented below.

Reflected in Table 8 is the level of communication skills in terms of behavioral communication skills with a corresponding mean of 3.96. Moreover, it is qualitatively interpreted and interpreted as high. This indicates that indicator is oftentimes manifested by the non-board program students.

Table 8. *Level of Communication Skills Terms of Behavioral Communication Skills*

<i>Behavioral Communication Skills</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Listening to the advice and suggestions driven by other people	4.19	High
2.	Sparing enough time to listen to what the people have to say	3.88	High
3.	Waiting patiently when others talk and I do not interrupt them	4.02	High
4.	Speaking clearly, using simple sentences	4.08	High
5.	Feeling free to take the first step in talking	3.61	High
Overall		3.96	High

Following this, it could be gleaned from the data that the item with the highest mean rating is 4.19 or High is item no. 1 –Listening to the advice and suggestions driven by other people. This signifies that this indicator is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. As opposed to this, the item with the lowest mean rating is 3.61 or High from the item no. 5 – Feeling free to take the first step in talking. This means that this indicator is oftentimes manifested by the non-board program students.

Summary on the Level of Communication Skills

The summary on the level of communication skills is presented, analyzed and interpreted below. The means of each indicator were presented below.

The results of the data of the level of communication skills in mental communication skills, emotional communication skills, and

behavioral communication skills is reflected in Table 9. The overall mean score is 3.88 which is described as high. This indicates that this variable is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Furthermore, it can be manifested in the table that indicator, behavioral communication skills got the highest mean of 3.96 or qualitatively described as high as perceived by the respondents, which means it is oftentimes manifested.

As opposed to this, the indicator, mental communication skills, got the lowest mean score of 2.83. This indicator is described as high. This indicates that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. Thus, the summary of the results of this stipulates that the communication skills of the non-board program students are oftentimes manifested.

Table 9. Summary on the Level of Communication Skills

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Mental Communication Skills	3.83	High
Emotional Communication Skills	3.85	High
Behavioral Communication Skills	3.96	High
Overall	3.88	High

Level of Home Environment in terms of Friendly Home Environment

The level of home environment in terms of friendly home environment was measured through survey questionnaire with the indicator assessment is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The response of the respondents was presented and analyzed.

Reflected in Table 10 is the level of home environment in terms of friendly home environment among college students with a corresponding overall mean of 3.98. the result indicates that the assessed item is qualitatively described and interpreted as high. This means that this indicator is oftentimes evident by the respondents.

It can be observed from the data that the item with the highest mean rating is 4.21. this item is no. 5 – Encouraging me in my learning. It pertains that the respondents oftentimes manifested this item.

As opposed to this, the item with the lowest score rating has 3.78 or interpreted as high is the item no. 4 – Cheering me to take part in my co-curricular activities. This signifies that this item is oftentimes evident by the respondents. The item with the second lowest mean rating is item no. 2 – Providing me with a favorable environment to improve my studies. This means that this item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 10. Level of Home Environment in Terms of Friendly Home Environment

<i>Friendly Home Environment</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Feeling like an essential part that boosts my confidence	3.94	High
2.	Providing me with a favorable environment to improve my studies	3.93	High
3.	Giving me pieces of advice on my mistakes	4.03	High
4.	Cheering me to take part in my co-curricular activities	3.78	High
5.	Encouraging me in my learning	4.21	High
Overall		3.98	High

Level of Home Environment in terms of Home Facilities

The level of home environment in terms of home facilities was measured through survey questionnaire with the indicator assessment is presented, analyzed and interpreted. The response of the respondents on the indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Reflected in the Table 11 is the level of home environment among non-board program students in terms of home facilities with a corresponding mean score of 3.81 which means that the results showed that this indicator is qualitatively described and interpreted as high. This indicator is oftentimes evident by the respondents.

It can be observed from the data that the item with the highest mean rating is item no. 2 – Providing me with all basic needs. The same thing is found in item no. 4 – Makes sure to provide us meals on time. Furthermore, these items are found oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 11. Level of Home Environment in Terms of Home Facilities

<i>Home Facilities</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Giving me a separate room for studies	3.56	High
2.	Providing me with all basic needs	4.07	High
3.	Providing me with WIFI which greatly helps me in my studies	3.77	High
4.	Making sure to provide us meals on time	4.07	High
5.	Providing me with educational textbooks	3.60	High
Overall		3.81	High

Level of Home Environment in terms of Parents Attention or Care

The level of home environment among college students in terms of parents attention or care is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The response of the respondents on the indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Reflected in the Table 12 is the level of home environment in terms of parents attention or care with a corresponding mean of 3.91 or qualitatively described as high. This indicator is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

It can be observed from the data that the item with the highest mean rating of 4.09 or interpreted as high is item no. 1 – Showing a positive attitude towards my studies. This item is characterized as oftentimes manifested. As opposed to this, the item with the lowest mean rating of 3.77 or described as high is item no. 3 – Discussing my academic career with me which greatly helps me. Hence, it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 12. *Level of Home Environment in Terms of Parents Attention or Care*

<i>Parents Attention or Care</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Showing a positive attitude towards my studies	4.09	High
2.	Helping me in all dimensions of my academic life	3.89	High
3.	Discussing my academic career with me which greatly helps me	3.77	High
4.	Demonstrating attentive parenting	3.80	High
5.	Creating a nurturing environment through giving us attention and love	4.00	High
Overall		3.91	High

Level of Home Environment in terms of Motivational Behavior of Parents

Reflected in Table 13 is the level of home environment in terms of motivational behavior or parents with a corresponding overall mean of 3.80. This indicator is qualitatively interpreted as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

It can be observed from the data that the item with the highest mean rating is 4.03 is item no. 1 – Giving positive remarks which stimulate my urge for academic achievements. Item no. 1 is qualitatively described and interpreted as high among college students particularly from non-board program students. This means that this item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

As opposed to this, the item with the lowest mean rating of 3.54 is item no. 4 – Valuing active listening, ensuring that each family member is heard and cared for. This item is qualitatively described and interpreted as high. This signifies that this item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 13. *Level of Home Environment in Terms of Motivational Behavior of Pare*

<i>Motivational Behavior of Parents</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Giving positive remarks which stimulate my urge for academic achievements	4.03	High
2.	Giving me rewards that uplifts my interest in my academic achievement	3.67	High
3.	Involving physical aspect in my studies which motivates me	3.89	High
4.	Valuing active listening, ensuring that each family member is heard and cared for	3.90	High
5.	Checking my homework and progress in my academic	3.54	High
Overall		3.80	High

Summary on the level of Home Environment

The summary on the level of home environment is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The mean results on each indicator were presented and analyzed.

The results on the level of home environment among college students is reflected in Table 14 with an overall mean score of 3.88 or qualitatively described and interpreted as high with the indicators to assess: friendly home environment, home facilities, parents' attention or care and motivational behavior of parents.

It can be observed in the data that the indicator, friendly home environment, got the highest mean score of 3.98. it is described and interpreted as high. Thus, it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 14. *Summary on Level of Home Environment*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Friendly Home Environment	3.98	High
Home Facilities	3.81	High
Parents Attention or Care	3.91	High
Motivational Behavior of Parents	3.80	High
Overall	3.88	High

Furthermore, the indicator, motivational behavior of parents, got the lowest mean score of 3.80. This indicator is qualitatively described and interpreted as high. Motivational behavior of parents is characterized as oftentimes manifested among the college students. Moreover, the second lowest mean score of 3.81 is the indicator home facilities. It is qualitatively described and interpreted as high. Thus, this means that this indicator is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Significant Relationship Between Language Learning Motivation and Communication Skills

As presented in the Table 15, the correlation between language learning motivation and communication skills. The results showed that $r = .633, p > .001$. At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis which states that there is no relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills among college students is rejected in this context. Thus, it stipulates that there is a significant relationship between variables language learning motivation and communication skills among college students at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 15. *Significant Relationship Between Language Learning Motivation and Communication Skills*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ = 0.05
Language Learning Motivation	3.86	.633	<.001	Ho Rejected
Communication Skills	3.88			

Significant Relationship Between Home Environment and Communication Skills

As presented in Table 16, the correlation between home environment and communication skills is $r = .553, p < .001$. Moreover, at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis states that there is a significant relationship between home environment and communication skills among college students is rejected. This stipulates that there is a significant relationship between the two variables at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 16. *Significant Relationship Between Role of Home Environment and Students' Communication Skills*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ = 0.05
Home Environment	3.88	.553	<.001	Ho Rejected
Students' Communication Skills	3.88			

Significant Relationship of Home Environment and Language Learning Motivation

As presented in Table 17, the correlation between home environment and language learning motivation is $r = 0.553, p < .001$. Moreover, at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis which states that there is no relationship between home environment and language learning motivation among college students is rejected in this context.

This stipulates that there is a significant relationship between the two variables. When it comes to communicating, home environment is critical to language learning motivation. Thus, home environment has a significant relationship on home environment as perceived by college students.

Table 17. *Significant Relationship Between Role of Home Environment and Language Learning Motivation*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ = 0.05
Home Environment	3.88	.503	<.001	Ho Rejected
Language Learning Motivation	3.86			

Mediation Analysis

This research employed the mediation analysis approach as developed by Preacher and Hayes, which emphasizes the examination of indirect effects. Specifically, this approach distinguishes between two types of mediation:

Table 18. *Indirect Effects*

Estimate	95% Confidence Interval		P	Lower	Upper	
	Std. Error	z-value				
IV→MV→DV	0.162	0.032	5.057	<0.001	0.099	0.225

In partial mediation, both direct and indirect effects from the independent variable (X) to the dependent variable (Y) are expected to be significant, implying that the relationship between X and Y is partially mediated by the mediator. Conversely, full mediation occurs when the mediator fully accounts for the relationship between X and the direct effect of X on Y becomes non-significant.

The significance of the indirect affect depends on the strength of the mediator’s effect on the relationship between X and Y. in cases here there are negligible relationships between mediator and X or Y, the mediation process is unlikely to occur.

It can be gleaned in the Table 18 the indirect effect of language learning motivation (IV) on home environment (MV) and on communication skills (DV). The result of the study yielded a beta of (B) .162 and standard error (SE) .032 with $p < .001$ or significant, (B=.162, SE=0.032, 95% CI [0.099, 0.225]). Also, as shown in the results, it could be inferred that in every unit increased in the language learning motivation (IV) will entice 0.162 to the communication skills (DV) as it goes through the home environment (MV). The results indicate that even in the presence of the mediating variable, which is the home environment, language learning motivation (IV) significantly influencing the communication skills (DV).

Furthermore, since home environment is the mediating variable, this indicates that language learning motivation and communication skills has an indirect effect on home environment. As language learning motivation increases, so does communication skills when there is a presence of home environment.

It can be observed in the Table 19 the direct effect of language learning motivation (IV) on communication skills (DV). The results yielded an estimate of 0.448 and standard error of 0.054 (SE), $p < 0.001$ or significant, (B=0.488, SE=0.054, 95% CI [0.383, 0.594]). In addition, it can be also observed that in every increase in language learning motivation (IV) will entice 0.488 increases in communication skills (DV). The results revealed that the language learning motivation (IV) is significantly influencing with the communication skills (DV). This indicates that the language learning motivation (IV) have a direct effect on communication skills (DV). Hence, as the language learning motivation (IV) increases, so does communication skills (DV).

Moreover, it can be observed in Table 20 the total effect of language learning motivation (IV) on communication skills (DV). The result yielded a beta of 0.651 and standard error (SE) of 0.050 with $p < 0.001$ or significant, (BE=0.651, 95% CI [0.554, 0.748]).

Table 19. Direct Effects

	95% Confidence Interval					
	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	P	Lower	Upper
IV→DV	0.488	0.054	9.097	<0.001	0.383	0.594

Also, as shown in the results, it could be conducted that in every increase in the language learning motivation (IV) will entice 0.651 to the communication skills (DV). Hence, it stipulates that, the language learning motivation (IV) significantly affect the communication skills (DV).

Table 20. Total Effect

	95% Confidence Interval					
	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	P	Lower	Upper
IV→DV	0.651	0.050	13.139	<0.001	0.554	0.748

The model in figure 1 showed the significant relationship between language learning motivation (IV) and communication skills (DV) through the mediating effect of home environment (MV). In Path A, language learning motivation has a significant relationship with home environment (MV), (B=0.59, $p < 0.001$). In Path B, home environment (MV) was also reported significantly correlated with communication skills (DV), (B=0.28, $p < 0.001$). In Path C, language learning motivation (IV) was positively predictive of communication skills (DV) (B=0.49, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 1. Medigraph Showing the Variable of the Study

Conclusions

These results revealed the relationship between language learning motivation (IV) and communication skills (DV) mediated by home environment. It was determined that self-efficacy got the lowest mean. Hence the following recommendations are provided. First, adopt peer learning and team reinforcement where students will be able to apply language skills and learn from one another, discuss learning procedures and motivate each other. Students should be urged to engage in the group discussions, the use of language exchange activities to enhance the students' morale and participation levels. The second recommendation is that they should encourage the students and also offer positive critiques on both their work and effort, potential and accomplishments. It employed the student's assets and achievements alongside offering them advice on how best they could develop and increase their linguistic abilities. Daily communications assist in informing the students which aspects they required to build up and develop.

In addition, among the indicators of communication skills, it was found out that mental communication skills got the lowest mean. Hence, the following recommendations are provided. The first recommendation is to employ activities like group discussion, debates, role-playing and think-pair-share. Through this, it will promote critical thinking, communication skills, and the ability to comprehend and understand different perspectives on specific matters. The second recommendation is to have a problem-based learning in which students are presented with complex, real-world problems or challenges in which they are required to think critically to analyze the problem and provide possible solutions and develop action plans. These activities promote and enhance mental communication in such a way that it requires students to think critically, formulate their thoughts, interact with others, and apply their gained knowledge and skills to real-world contexts.

Furthermore, it was found out that the indicator, motivational behaviors of parents got the lowest mean rating among the indicators of home environment. Hence, the following are provided. The first recommendation is to enhance parental involvement. Parents should engage in discussions about education, provide support, and create a conducive environment for learning at home. By so doing, it increases motivation to students in their studies. The second recommendation is therefore touching on such aspects as the interaction between the parents and students. This makes it very important to encourage the students to freely communicate with their teachers and peers in relation to their motivation. Ideally, parents have a nice duty of talking to their children concerning their studies progress, plans, and difficulties. With this, feedback can be regarded as: promoting and providing endorsement.

Finally, future researchers are encouraged to explore additional variables, such as the school environment, which may mediate the relationship between language learning motivation and communication skills among college students. It is also recommended to broaden the focus of respondents to include individuals from other programs or institutions. This approach could provide new insights and data regarding the variables examined in this study. Additionally, examining the role of extracurricular activities and peer interactions could further enrich the understanding of these dynamics. Such comprehensive research could contribute significantly to the development of more effective educational strategies and interventions.

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